

3D Printed Assistive Technology among Multiple Control Sites

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Abstract— In the current context, assistive technology is important to provide resources that allow people with some motor disability to perform tasks that were previously almost impossible. This project aims to present the development of an assistive technology system using 3D printing, achievable to reproduce, redesign and low cost of the structural model. The literature presents several studies whose system control is automated or have only one control site method, a fact that can make it possible to perform unwanted actions by the user. In the present project, it was decided to carry out acquisitions of two different control sites from user commands: movements from the user's jaw or lips and head. To avoid control errors and intuitive control increases. Thus, applications such as navigation in virtual interfaces, control of a wheelchair or robotic limbs are aimed. The device is composed of different parts being processing and communication hardware, sensors and 3D printed mechanical structure. The 3D structure was designed to interconnect the sensors and the processing and communication hardware in a single physical structure, and that guarantees a strategic positioning of the sensors. The device has sensors, such as an inertial sensor that detects the movements of the head, and the joystick for detecting the movements of the jaw or lips. Finally, the device allows this detected data to be processed and sent to the receiving system by various communication protocol methods: WIFI, Bluetooth or USB.

Keywords — Assistive Technology, Quality of Life, Head Gesture, 3D Printer.

I. INTRODUCTION

Many diseases imply the loss of movement of lower limbs, upper limbs and even the torso. Brain stroke, quadriplegia, amputation limbs and amyotrophic lateral sclerosis are some examples which disable the subject to have an independent and autonomous life [1]. In other words, those severe diseases which leads to total movement loss can be described as Locked-in syndrome (LIS). This impairment is a process where the brain is fully functional and the individual is conscious, but the body is nonfunctional [2].

Persons with physical disabilities with a severe degree of disability are unable to perform daily functions such as eating, bathing, and moving [3]. This fact brings up a social responsibility where the technology comes to facilitate the personal activities of daily living and developing inclusion of the impaired individuals in social, professional, and cultural areas of life [4,5].

Assistive Technologies (AT) are equipment and devices that benefit from human-machine interaction. Their main function is providing the individual to move around, communicate and interact with the environment [5]. The AT can be divided into mechanical and electronic sections. Mechanical approach holds actions as seating, doing personal activities of daily living and electric approach is considered computer access, communication aids and environmental control [5].

Lately, several studies have shown self-help technologies, such as wheelchairs integrated with specific electronic, sensory, and mechanical systems [3,4,6], human-machine wireless communication methods [7], meal assistance system [8] and exoskeletons managed by control sites: eye movements, finger pressure and processed EEG signals [9,10].

As Internet of Things (IoT) has the potential to provide better services for people with disabilities by providing emphasis on proactive health monitoring and self-management. It becomes possible AT be a powerful tool to help achieve a better quality of life, increase independence, and improve participation of the disabled people in social and economic life [11].

In this research field, there is a term commonly used “control site”. The control site is considered which body part or physical action the user must use to operate the self-help technology. In other words, the control site can be a hand or a finger, voice, mouth, head, or eyes and more. And, from the control site the user manages the interaction with the machine: touchscreen, pointer, or keyboard [12]. But among all studies in state-of-the-art there are considered any or only one control site. It can result in unexpected system responses and non-intuitive interface handling by the individual [4,5,7].

In this line, this paper will explore two control sites: the jaw of facial region, tongue movements and head movements to access and manage the pointer from the computer. The main objective is an AT development of joystick and inertial sensor with less effort from impaired individuals and higher efficiency of response by the computer. In addition, separately, the head movement up and down is responsible for pointer enter. The division between two control sites avoids errors and makes it more intuitive when handling the equipment.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Hardware Modeling

Among the various embedded platforms for prototyping the assistive system control, a hardware that features an ESP32-C3 microcontroller (LilyGo-T-OI-PLUS) was used in this work. This hardware proved to be quite versatile for integrating the assistive technology system to interface with mobile devices (smartphone, tablet) and computers, because it contains different forms of communication with these devices.

In addition to the communication and processing hardware, sensors were used to detect the movement performed by the user. To detect the rotation movement (Roll) of the user's head, the MPU-6050 inertial sensor was used to obtain acceleration data. For user navigation control, it is done using the joystick, which from the movements performed by the jaw or lips, it can navigate through a cursor in a virtual environment or control the movements of a wheelchair.

B. Project Structure

The developed project consists of different parts, which together form an assistive technology system for human-machine interface. Among these parts is presenting hardware with the processing, communication, sensing and power components. For the interconnection of these different hardware, a 3D structure was designed for the strategic positioning of the components, mainly the sensors for detecting jaw, tongue or lip movements, and the entire head. For a better illustration of this 3D structure, Figure 1 and 2 3D modeling of all the parts that make up the structure and presents the dispositive dimensions, respectively. The Fusion 360 software was used to model this device.

In the modeling of the prototype, the total length of the human face was considered, on average, the proportions are 1/3 for the respective points: chin-nose, nose-eyebrows, and eyebrows-scalp. Then, chin-nose is subdivided into 1/3 mouth-nose and 2/3 mouth-chin. From these proportions, the dimensioning of the device was carried out. The dimensional parameters used were based on the measurement for use by one of the team members. Therefore, the dimensions were approximately 138 mm for height from the base of the forehead to the chin stick. The internal width was given at 137.9 mm. Adjustable upper and lower side rods are 115 mm and 80.4 mm respectively. In the upper and lower side rods, there are holes with a distance between the centers of 7.2 mm, which allow an optimal adjustment of the height in relation to the contact of the jaw or lips with the joystick sensor.

Fig. 1. Illustration 3D modeling of the mechanical structure of the assistive device.

Fig. 2. Illustration of dispositive dimensions in millimeters

This 3D structure was developed to be fixed on the user's forehead, and that provides ergonomics in its use and is functional. However, it is necessary a qualitative validation of the device in the day-to-day of the user, to evaluate how much is ergonomic and functional.

C. Communication Protocol

The assistive technology system developed can communicate between a human-machine interface, using wireless communication protocols such as Bluetooth, or WIFI, or by communication through physical wired connection such as USB serial. This hardware has versatility of communication options, as well as for the possibility of integration of different sensors, which will allow control emulating a mouse cursor, for example, by the control of different sites by the user.

III. RESULTS

The Figure 3 shows the complete assembly of the assistive technology device, and the components that are place in the dispositive containing: joystick, inertial sensor and processor and communication unit. The joystick base is adjustable to have contact with user's jaw. The subject can use the jaw movement or lips movement as preferred to move and control the joystick. The Figure 4 presents an illustration of the spatial navigation in joystick control by the user. This control can be a pointer in screen, a navigation of robotic-arm or a wheelchair guidance.

The inertial sensor is positioned on top of the head. As a neutral anatomical position, the inertial sensor has the origin of X, Y and Z axes. Once the head movement occurs, the inertial sensor changes its coordinates and an action in system is made. The Figure 5 illustrates the second control site by the user regarding the inertial sensor axis. It makes possible infer differently actions for the system as: click/enter of a mouse, open, and close a hand in robotic-arm and stop and go for a wheelchair.

For the communication methods this study validates the structured with USB serial communication in a screen navigation in computer. The main point of the present assistive technology is there is no need in upper-limbs or lower-limbs movements to use this technology. Thus, separating final actions in receptor system into different control sites, makes the use more intuitive and less vulnerable of faulty actions during the use.

Fig. 3. Components that make up the device being these: inertial sensor, joystick, communications and processor.

Fig. 4. Representation of the spatial navigation joystick control.

Fig. 5. Roll head movements, as second control site, regarding inertial sensor axis.

IV. DISCUSSION

There are studies in the literature that do not use any control system by the user, that is, automated systems such as wheelchairs following line or that avoid obstacles [4,5]. And there are studies that use means of control by the user, but only a single means control, such as device coupled to the user with

inertial sensor, eye movement, or physiological signs [1,7]. As well as the development of communication systems that accept only one method, such as Bluetooth [3].

The present study aims to cover the control sites presented to the individual with mandible and head movements, totaling two types of control, simulating the functionalities of a mouse from computer. Thus, as an added advantage this device allows different communication methods such as Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, and USB.

This fact allows the device to interact with several systems depending on the user's interest in control and commands. Thus, we can highlight the possibility of human-machine interface with serious games, operating systems, control with external devices such as robotic arms and wheelchairs. The mechanical structure of the device is adjustable and adaptable to the bone structure of the individual so that it allows ergonomic and comfortable use. Another advantage is that the structure is replicable and can re-engineered as needed using 3D printing technology.

V. LIMITATIONS

The present project has the following limitations: lack of adherence to the joystick sensor, allowing it not to have more precise movements, with a high degree of resolution. It was also analyzed the need for improvements in the fixation of the device in relation to the user's forehead, having to contain one more fixation point, such as on top of the head, to provide better mechanical stability for use. It will be necessary to have tests directed to the public of interest, for qualitative validation in their day to day, in relation to ergonomics and functionality of the prototype, to quantify the points needed to be improved.

As future work, it is intended to validate assistive technology, present data accuracy of assertive executions of system actions according to the user's intention and system response time. Thus, forward we aim improvements in the hardware structure, such as joystick replacement, with a lower mechanical stiffness, allowing smoother movements by the user. Constructing a firmware which provides to user a versatility of choosing the communication protocol of his preference, among which the embedded technology allows, which are WIFI, Bluetooth or USB. And will be implemented the use of this device in more applications, such as human-machine interface in the control of wheelchairs and robotic arms for example.

VI. CONCLUSION

The developed assistive technology comprises two control sites: joystick and inertial sensor. Exploring, in this way, the jaw, lips and head movements can be used to access and manage the control of human-machine interface. Initially, it is considered as a pointer from the computer device which can serve in many applications such as use of mobile devices and computers.

This assistive technology focus on people who have motor limitation in the upper limbs, such as quadriplegic people. In addition, as advantage of this study is the possibility of replication and redesign its construction. Because it is composed of 3D printing for its production, a technology that is becoming increasingly common and accessible.

Therefore, in future works, the aim is to validate ergonomics by users, to verify points to be improved to ensure greater comfort. Thus, from a satisfaction scale, the user will

measure topics such as comfort, functionality, and durability. This qualitative analysis will allow for improvements in the developed assistive technology.

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